

INFLUENCE OF WORKING CONDITIONS ON TEACHER ATTRITION IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN UASIN GISHU COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract:

This paper investigates how working conditions in the schools influences teacher attrition. The working condition in schools refers to the school environment / climate that would in one way or other make teachers to have turnover intentions. This study was conducted in Uasin Gishu County that has faced increased rates of teacher attrition in addition to teacher shortages. To answer the research objective, a convergent parallel mixed method approach design was utilised. Data was collected from public secondary schools involving Form 3 and Form 4 students, teachers, principals, county education officials and teachers who had left the profession. The study collected data through use of questionnaire and interview schedule were used to collect data. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics. Research result showed that the following working conditions; indiscipline situation in schools among students, inadequate infrastructure and instructional resources, political interference, ethnicity, poor leadership, heavy workload among others influenced teacher attrition in schools. The study also found out that movement of teachers from schools located in the interior also fuelled attrition rate. The study recommends that Ministry of Education and the Teachers' Service Commission should review the policy on the election of school prefects and hire professional counsellors for public secondary schools to deal with discipline related issues.

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1. Introduction

The teacher attrition issue is an area of great concern not only in the education sector and school environment but also among all other stakeholders in Education system (Goldring, Taie & Riddles, 2014). Attrition is a component of teacher turnover, in which either employees leave a profession voluntarily or involuntarily (Armstrong, 2009). In this case, teachers who voluntarily leave the profession have an alternative job market while those who involuntarily leave results from the age factor. In the school environment, teachers comprise the central part of the system, an issue confirmed globally to have an effect on the students' academic performance (Barnett, 2017). They facilitate the learning process of learners as well as the quality and retention of children in schools. The need for qualified, well-inspired and maintained teachers is an important factor for student's school learning environment. Quality teaching and learning sturdily controls the learners' consumption in their academic achievement (Ingersoll & May, 2011). The experience of teacher turnover in both developed and developing countries is a phenomenon that worries all stakeholders in the education sector. In this case, it needs an urgent attention and address if the economic status of a nation has to develop (Ingersoll, 2012). According to Saleem and Gul (2013), teacher attrition has become a critical phenomenon worldwide when a large number of qualified and most experienced teachers leave the profession each year. This according to Agezo (2010) puts the most vulnerable learners at a risk in failing to realize quality education for their future career opportunities. Dalgic (2014) on the same view established that a number good of learning institutions have suffered educator turnover which definitely has serious negative effects on students' academic achievement. Ariko and Othuon (2014) noted that teacher transfer requests in Suba, Sub-county of Homa-bay County in Kenya, were at 16.5%. The figures according to them were high and above the national annual average of 5% which had a serious influence on the learners' academic performance. The Education Ministry in Kenya (MoE, 2011), during Education Day in Eldoret Town, raised a lot of concern on the rates of teacher attrition in the county despite it having high socio- economic indicators that could possibly influence stability in schools. In order to plan for teacher recruitment and employment, the factors that contribute to attrition issues need urgent consideration. This paper settles on identifying how working conditions influence teacher attrition in public secondary schools in Uasin Gishu County.

2. Problem statement

The role played by teachers in the provision of quality teaching is of great value and needs recognition. However, the education sector has a serious problem of losing thousands of dedicated personnel to other sectors consistently, putting most students at risk and vulnerable to fail. In Kenya, the Teachers' Service Commission (2010)

recognized that over 10000 teachers lost annually hindered curriculum implementation, disrupted continuity in the learning process and negatively affected learners' academic achievement. Uasin Gishu County, the general teacher attrition and turnover is overwhelmingly high leading to teacher shortage in most public secondary schools. This paper looked at whether working conditions in secondary schools influenced the trend.

2.1 Purpose of the paper

The purpose of this paper is to investigate how working conditions influence attrition of teachers in public secondary schools in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya.

3. Literature review

In the teaching profession, certain factors are beyond the control of the teacher and fall within the institution of teaching fraternity. Such factor include working environment, policies on discipline, policies on teacher transfer, amount of workload each teacher is assigned, teacher management and supervision among many others. As Chang, *et al.*, (2010) puts it, understanding the effect of working conditions on the teachers' day-to-day professional activities will have the power to provide precise, explicit, and measurable goals to work toward. They further observed that some working conditions would have a positive effect on the teachers' commitment, whereas others have a negative effect. A study by Kayuni and Tambulasi (2007), established that for the past 10 to 20 years working conditions emerged as the major source of teacher job dissatisfaction and attrition in public secondary schools in Malawi.

Other studies confirmed that teacher's perceptions on favourable working conditions are related to higher job satisfaction in terms of salary, fringe benefits, administrative support, school management and leadership, as well as workload. It perceived that teachers are lowly paid as compared to other workers in other organizations with the same level of education. World Bank (2010) revealed that, teachers in sub-Saharan countries are not motivated because of poor remuneration. Good remuneration is an explanation for deterioration of teachers' morale and motivation in the profession. The decline of self-esteem and motivation in Africa is a result of having responsibilities that cause teachers to search for green pastures in private institutions. Other studies have shown that despite some increment in salary in some countries, most primary and secondary school teachers, particularly in relatively high-cost urban centres, are simply unable to meet their basic household needs. As a result, many are forced to find other sources of income and it is impossible to earn an additional income go down into poverty.

In addition, UNESCO (2010) observes that in countries with implementation of educational reforms which may influence the teachers' satisfaction, it is imperative to explore the views of the teachers on their working conditions, and the impact of these conditions on their job satisfaction. The teachers' job satisfaction has implications for the quality education they provide. This information could assist education leaders,

programme implementers and other significant stakeholders to make evidence-based decisions about how best to design the school-working environment and maximize positive outcomes for children, teachers and general school environment.

Teachers' salaries in low-income countries have declined in both absolute and relative terms. According to Gupta (2010), in many countries, the schools have been expanded, yet teachers' salaries have been eroded which has a direct effect on the attendance, motivation and performance of teachers and consequently leads to poor quality of education. Wages and salaries in the teaching profession should be in line with those for comparable jobs in other professions, otherwise the Education sector would not be able to attract and retain competent personnel.

The working conditions could be physical and psychological factors so long they surround the teacher's job, which in their nature act as motivators in working place. Therefore, missing such motivating factors teachers will quit the profession. A study by Goldring, Taie and Riddles (2014) revealed that a good teacher is a key to student success and the school environment conditions can enhance a teacher's performance and increase retention. Employee engagement includes elements within the workplace environment that, attract, focus and keep the most talented employees (Boyd, et al., 2011). According to Darling-Hammond (2010), a good working environment include teacher support, mentoring administrative efforts to create positive school culture that provide opportunities for teachers to engage in collegial collaboration focused on instruction and working conditions that provide teachers with resources.

A study by Maicibi (2006) established that common reasons for employee as; poor management and supervisors who provide poor leadership to employees like inequality, unfair treatment among others, even though salaries are important, working conditions are seen as extremely important in teacher turnover. On similar observation, Haldar (2010) indicates that leaders with coercive type of supervision create in employees' feelings that they are not trustworthy. In such incidences when the phenomenon is consistently applied, it obvious becomes de motivation and the work interest eroded. If supervision is too coercive, the morale of the teacher is affected hence poor performance.

A considerable school principal creates confidence in his/her juniors to participate in major school decision-making processes. According to Buchanan (2012), indicators for de-motivation in a teacher include low output and productivity, frustration and unrest in the work place, deviant and violent behaviour, and frequent confrontations with their school principals, incitement and violent demonstrations and finally increases excessive teacher turnover. Buchanan further observes that when employees work under poor management conditions, tend to behave like caged animals looking for the slightest opportunity to escape from such a situation when an opportunity opens whether less than the present job they leave without regret.

In another study by Swars, Meyers, Mays and Lack (2009), on perennial problems leading to teacher turnover, it revealed that attrition had roots in the intense stress that many teachers face on a daily basis. According to the study, attrition leads to job burnout, which pushes many new teachers out of the profession and that teacher

retention in schools with a stable leadership was higher as compared to schools with changing principals. Adequate teaching and learning resources builds confidence and competent in teachers. In the United States, Curtis (2012) carried out a study to examine the reasons why mathematics teachers never entered the teaching profession and compared those reasons with their reasons for leaving the profession of instruction. The study indicated that mathematics and science teachers, along with teachers of special and bilingual education, left the teaching profession at higher rates than those in other fields, while in the UK, English, music, and physical education teachers also appeared to leave at higher rates. The reason cited was due the poor working environment, lack of resources and strained relationship with the school management. The current study filled the gap by finding the critical factors besides the mentioned ones that contribute to teacher attrition in Uasin Gishu County public secondary schools.

A survey carried out by Ladd (2011) on teachers in North Carolina to establish the connection between teaching staff working conditions, and teacher mobility concluded that teachers' perception of their working conditions could be used to project attrition. That includes two components of teachers' work, which are the environment, and socio-economic makeup of the school population. The study further revealed that the high rates of teacher turnover in public schools was caused by poor standards of students' behaviour, that is, the general indiscipline and violent behaviour from the community, which made teachers leave the teaching profession.

The teachers' living condition is not attractive due lack of appropriate accommodation in school environment and walking long distances which sometimes contribute to absenteeism, lateness and attrition. Mulkeen (2010) observed that some schools' physical structures are not attractive and that the class sizes are very large. Although the ideal average Pupil-Teacher Ratio (PTR) at secondary school level is 40; 1,, they vary from school to school depending on the location of the school, the sufficiency of classrooms and the number of teachers. Those with enough teachers especially in urban areas, have relatively low PTR and subsequently small class sizes. In Kenya, Mulei (2012), established that schools in Mbooni East District few classrooms, several streams of the same class are combined to form one class which is very large and results to unhealthy learning and teaching environment. Lack of cooperation from all education stakeholders creates unfavourable working environment in schools. Bryk and Schneider (2005) in a study on factors contributing to teacher attrition in the education sector, found out that the quality of relationships (trust) that exist between teachers, students, and the school principal are some of the issues that determine the academic achievement and performance of the students. Rockoff (2004) in a similar study found out that high teacher turnover rates contribute to school instability and continuity in learning, making it hard to have coherent instruction. This weakness becomes particularly problematic in schools, which are trying to implement reforms, as new teachers coming in each year are likely to repeat mistakes, rather than improve the participation in the reform implementation Processes.

Adera and Bullock (2010) cites poor teacher management practices as one of the major causes of teacher attrition. When teachers are not given the right guidance,

positive appraisal, personal problems understood within the school set up or they are frustrated or stressed by unfavourable conditions and eventually lose morale and low job satisfaction which fuel their desire to quit or look for alternative employment. The study here wished to establish to what extent the mode of supervision from the principals and to some extent, the education officials in the county influence teacher attrition. Okungu (2012) established that working conditions determine principals' management styles and high affinity influences occupational attrition among teachers. He observed that when teachers worked for long extra hours without appropriate overtime payment and the inconsistent management styles of principals created poor working conditions, which contributed to the influence of teacher attrition. In addition, Cherop (2014) revealed that increased workloads made it difficult for the teachers to cope and eventually this fuels teacher's desire to leave for greener pastures or movement to private sector or career switch in a bid to look for better paying jobs that are not cumbersome and rates of returns are higher than in teaching. The researcher here wished to establish the workload for teachers from different departments with a view to determine whether this was one of the factors that influenced teacher attrition.

Most schools have high expectations on the teachers' productivity. This accountability to parents, school heads, the county and national government influences attrition when the expectations cannot be achieved. According to Salifu, (2014), poor measures for accountability leads to poor working conditions, creates strained relationships, which affects the quality of teaching and learning. Ngala and Nyakwara (2017) explored the school related factors influencing teacher attrition in schools in Kengeleni zone' Mombasa County. The study found out that when the politicians interfere with the teaching and learning in schools, it affects nearly all aspects of job motivation including recruitment, deployment, promotion and management. This creates a very harsh working environment for both teachers and students. The study-established attrition was caused by many school related factors, including poor school management, inadequate school facilities and administrative support.

4. Materials and methods

This study adopted a convergent parallel mixed methods research design. In this case, the quantitative and qualitative methods complement each other, and provide for the triangulation of findings, hence greater validity of the emerging inferences. The research was carried out in Uasin Gishu County which is one of the 47 counties of Kenya. The county has six Sub- Counties namely; Ainabkoi, Kapseret, Kesses, Turbo, Soy and Moiben. This study targeted 166 public secondary schools, 2732 form 3 and 4 students, 1792 teachers, 166 principals and 6 County Education officials in Uasin Gishu County. The researcher chose to involve 30 teachers who had left the teaching profession for other reasons different from natural attrition and normal retirement. To determine the sample size for principals, 10% of the total population was used to act as a sample size. Data was collected using a questionnaire, interview schedule and document checklist. Data from the field was analyzed using qualitative and quantitative

techniques. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics for all quantitative data. Qualitative data from the open-ended questions and the data from the interview schedule were analyzed thematically and used the grounded theory procedures.

5. Findings and discussions

5.1 Teacher Attrition in Public Secondary Schools

The study sought information from the respondents on the rate at which teachers were leaving the teaching profession in the county. This was an important variable as it assisted the researcher to predict the effect of the phenomena on the students' academic performance after the years covered by the current study. The sampled teachers on service were asked to indicate the rate of attrition in their respective schools. The teacher were to rank the teacher attrition rates as; extremely high, high, somehow high, low and very low. The responses are shown in Figure 1;

Figure 1: Attrition Rate of Teachers

(Source: Field Data (2017))

As shown in Figure 1, accumulatively majority 63.4. % of the teachers indicated that teacher attrition was somehow high, high and extremely high while only 37% cited low and very low. Based on the data it is clear that attrition is quite high in Uasin Gishu County. Majority of the students 73% who took part in the study indicated attrition is very high, high or moderate while a small number 20% low echoed the same. This was in line agreement with the respondents reported. However, the County Director of Education's office and some of sampled school principals did not have the exact number of teachers as some of the teachers left without information or notice. In this case, the researcher used the teachers' information as significant and reliable. An excerpt from one of the education official states; at times, you are not even aware that a teacher has left. An incident at hand last year one of teachers left for Australia because

he had been recruited as a trainer in athletics, the school principal and the office was not aware, only to learn later the teacher had received scholarships for studies in athletics abroad (Interview Conducted on 13th September, 2017).

Having examined the trend of attrition in the county, the researcher sought to investigate the factors that contributed teacher attrition. Teacher attrition in public secondary schools is varied, and each individual teacher's decision to leave teaching is influenced by different reasons. The data was from students, teachers, principals of the sampled schools and the Ministry of Education Officials at the County level. The results are presented in the following sub-sections.

The teachers on duty were asked to rate their observation on a scale as; not likely(1), less likely(2), undecided(3), likely(4) and most likely(5) on factors that contribute to teacher attrition in their schools. The results of the analysis are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Teachers' Views on Factors Contributing to Attrition

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Unfriendly working conditions	273	3.6081	1.34364
Students' behaviour and discipline	273	3.3663	1.55933
School leadership and administration	273	3.2601	1.43555
Lack of professional respect in school	273	3.0000	1.50977
Teachers are not involved in decisions making	273	2.8974	1.37617
Political interference in school management	273	2.8352	1.63327
Working relationship with principals	273	2.7985	1.55052
New teachers lack induction and mentoring in the school system	273	2.7912	1.36541
Class size	273	2.7692	1.43801
Resources/ Facilities	273	2.6593	1.35489
Lack of collegiality and collaboration with colleagues	273	2.5751	1.42549
Valid N (List wise)	273		

Out of 273 respondents, on average (M=3.78 and SD=1.39 most likely) cited that poor remuneration and unfriendly working conditions, another considerable number (M=3.36 and SD=5.55), of teachers indicated students' behaviour, lack of professional respect, teachers not involved in decision making and political interference in school management while (M= 3.2 and SD= 1.4 less likely) reported poor relationship with school administration, lack of induction and mentoring programs and class size as factors and lastly on the statement of lack of collegiality and collaboration with colleagues, was slightly below average (M=2.36 and SD=1.17 less likely). This shows that teamwork and consultation within the staff did not influence attrition much.

According to the respondents, consultation among members of staff was looked as a sign of incompetence. The finding also shows that lack of adequate resources and facilities was rated (M=2.57 and SD=1.42). Teachers who had favourable views on facilities and resources emphasized the need to address structural problems and an increase in the limited resources to facilitate quality teaching and learning. Most the data findings in Table 9, was in line with what many of the sampled principals and the

teachers who had left the profession reported. However, there were few variations between teachers who had left and principals on other factors that contributed to attrition. This can be attributed to the fact the teachers who had left had factual factors that contributed to their departure. A considerable number cited ethnicity while majority 63% of the principals cited performance pressure from the employer made teachers leave the profession. The principals observed that the performance contracting (PC), Teacher Appraisal, and Development are well intended mechanisms put by the Teachers' Service Commission to empower teachers regain the lost glory of the profession and earn public confidence and support. However, the pressure on proper documentation on teachers' professional records, such as checking learners' work, lesson plan, and scheme of work, lesson observation records and others that must be updated regularly contributes to attrition.

The teachers' delivery is compromised where many get discouraged and leave the profession. The study findings are further in line with a study by Ingersoll (2010), which attributes class size where large population of learners contributes to teachers' decision in quitting teaching. Goblin (2008) also found that when teachers have many learners in a class, they try to look for any possible means to leave the stations echoes this finding. All the cited factors were in line with what the teachers who had left the profession and the County Education officials reported.

A vast majority of the teachers and sampled school principals felt that the school environment did not allow them to develop their full potential. Based on the observation, it showed that teachers' lack of development skills in their specific fields was a major factor as to why some good and experienced teachers leave the profession, while those who remain believed that their status and recognition in society was poor. According to the teachers, this was unfair treatment, which dissatisfied them in the profession and therefore a decision to quit. Politics in management of schools was another factor reported that influences attrition in schools especially in terms of promotion to headship. The finding indicate that promotion opportunities and practices in the County are unfair, and discriminated against many of them, as was based on party affiliation or ethnicity and inter personal relationship with the management. A general comment from the teachers was that, *"a hardworking and outstanding teacher is never rewarded while an ineffective and irresponsible one is promoted"*. However, on the students' behaviour and discipline, majority of the teachers indicated that, the relationship between teachers and students depended on how the teachers treated the students. If the teachers treated their students fairly, and prepared themselves well for their lessons, the students respected them, and behaved well. This is a very important score as it shows that the students' lack of discipline was not an issue for attrition in many of the public secondary schools in the county as it depended on an individual teachers' relationship with the learners.

On the other hand, majority of the sampled principals and few teachers appeared not quite happy about the students' behaviour and discipline. An excerpt from one of the principals' observation as quoted states;

“As a head of an institution, I know very well that I have to account for all the school property and it is my role as a principal to provide protection on my teachers. Unfortunately, the populist policies including delocalization of teachers and excessive pressure on students to deliver are making learners to vent their anger on teachers and destroy property. This type of distraction and disruptive scare teachers and even most of the upcoming generation may not want to join the teaching fraternity.” (Interview Conducted in 24th September, 2017)

The observation made by the principals was consistent with what all other principals’ observed. This seems to imply that certain factors might have been overlooked before the implementation of the policy. This is a very important score in the study as it showed that the students’ lack of discipline emerged from the government policy, an issue that is worthy evaluation. On the same issue, most of the teachers who had left teaching strongly observed that the new policy on the students’ selection to leadership needs to be re-evaluated. An excerpt from one of the key informant;

“As a teacher who has been in the profession for over thirty years, The Education Act 2010 that gave students much freedom in school management and administration is the genesis of numerous distractive and disruptive activities in schools. Students’ unrest is a thorny issue causing loss of property, lives and wastage of valuable study time, forcing the scholars to snap their heads to establish the causes and mitigation thereof. Actually, I left teaching because of the threats from the students I taught” (Interview Conducted on 2nd October, 2017)

The findings indicate that students’ have lost direction in the academic fields. It is the responsibility of the Ministry of Education (MOE) and the Teachers Service Commission (TSC) to identify and post teachers to schools not students. Majority of teachers who were on duty and those who had left the profession indicated that most students in the schools had no interest in learning and cited the most prominent factors as peer pressure, school leadership and teachers’ management as some influences of discipline cases in schools. They do not follow their lessons attentively and at times are absent from school, basing this lack of interest in learning on many contributing factors, namely the education policy, the curriculum, their family and the contemporary life style in society. Few teachers cited unfavourable comparison remarks made by older and experienced teachers on students. For instance, some older/ experienced teachers at times compare the students’ attitudes with their own when they were in school. This in most occasions creates poor relationships between the students and the said teachers, which influences the decisions of quitting the school or the profession.

On the other hand, some keen teachers and principals observed that the modern students have more power than teachers do. Most of the students have more time to evaluate and report teachers’ misconduct and behaviour than showing commitment in their education. The teachers would want to teach but students’ interest demoralizes

them and they quit. The general observation was that it was very hard to produce good results in certain schools within the county because students in these schools are more interested in outdoor activities than class work. An example of an excerpt as captured from a respondent;

“You work hard to prepare lessons for your students, and then in class only a few are hopeful about the future. The majority of them do not have any interest in learning. Their interest is in co curricula activities and particularly sports. At times some can be absent from school for a whole month. Most of the time students have the mentality of this slogan; “A County of Champions”. Therefore, with this type of attitude one feels frustrated and opts to quit. Since at end it is the teacher who will be accountable for the poor results. A good number of students and parents in the county believe that sports are a shortcut to an economic development.”(Interview Conducted on 20th September, 2017)

The findings indicate that students’ reading culture in certain schools particularly day schools in the county was a problem. The teachers’ general observation was that majority of the students in the sub-county schools had no interest in learning citing the most prominent factor as being lack of basic knowledge and skills in their subjects. They are just in class to fulfil the wish of the government and that their lack of interest to learn was because of the entry behaviour and many other related factors, namely the education policy that encourages the development of talent, the curriculum, their family and the society. This is in line with the importance the government puts in co- curricular activities as reported by Asa (2018) in the Education Newspaper, that the government will improve on funding and other logistics to ensure more children participate in Kenya Music Festivals in future.

During an interaction with the teachers who had left, one of the teachers recalled a painful experience as a teacher in one of the schools in the county. The teacher narrated how she lost all her family members during the political unrest in the region in 2007 and that, her social interaction with the learners in the school was strictly monitored. Succinctly was always treated with suspicion whenever she was seen interacting with her students, which made the teacher lose, interest working in the area and opted to resign.

In a similar instance, there was general observation from the teachers who had left that most of them had not been in any leadership positions except two teachers who had a normal retirement. One of the teacher respondents had a keen observation on the promotion of teachers as quoted;

“In this county, one cannot be promotion to headship, as it is not based on efficiency and experience alone. There are other hidden criterions followed. Imagine I was in my former school for eight full years; I had attained the required job group N, in this case was qualified to be a principal or a deputy but then was assigned by the school Board of Management(BOM) several managerial positions; the Director of studies member of

disciplinary panel and games master. All these were extra responsibilities minus any reward. I found it extremely hard to work without terms of preference, sought for study leave and now I run family business in town here. I preferred to quit and never wish to go back."(Responses from interview on 13th September, 2017)

Most of the teachers who had left teaching from the county cited deployment to remote areas and poor remuneration as a factor that made them quit. The teachers' argument was that they once deployed to areas presumed to be hardship and difficult to access basic needs for their families, social amenities, no clean water and their security was not a grantee. This was in agreement with what the Education officials in an interview session said that many teachers once deployed to areas that was perceived to be a security threat, would rush to seek for transfers or resign from the profession altogether. As reported, some of those areas were insecure and teachers claimed that there was insufficient housing.

In an open-ended statement, the teachers and sampled principals reported that in some schools it was very difficult to get a decent house to stay. One of the teachers explained on how during the rainy season, he moved into an abandoned building when the roof was falling in the rented house he lived which even lacked toilet facilities. As reported, some of those areas were insecure and teachers claimed that there were insufficient facilities for teaching and learning. In most of these schools, principals shared offices with the staff and most of the teachers were not free. Some of the teacher respondents indicated that in some schools, principals scorned at teachers in the presence of the whole staff with no regard to the teacher's self-esteem. The issue on teachers' professional ethics seemed to be on the rise in the county. The sampled principals and the sub-County Directors of education reported that there were cases of unprofessional conducts from teachers in some schools in the County. The unethical issues were absenteeism, desertion, sexual harassment, insubordination and mismanagement of school resources. However one-education official, who seemed to have had bad incidences in his sub- County, narrated how unprofessional ethos had influenced few teachers in the sub-county to an extent of leaving the profession. According to the officials' report, the code of regulation for teachers stipulates very clearly the conduct of a teacher in the profession. In this case, once a teacher goes against the code of conduct for instance one who is amorously in relationship with learners, constantly absent from duty, faces disciplinary action. The same sentiments were in consistent with reports from some sampled principals.

In terms of lack of enough resources and facilities, most of the teachers interviewed, reported that it was very hard to prepare students for a national examination with practical section in the schools. On their part, most the school principals agreed that their effectiveness in ensuring improved students' academic performance in the schools enough resources were necessary. However, their hands were tired as they depended on funds from the national government. An excerpt from a chemistry teacher who had left teaching;

“At times, a teacher wants students to perform well in sciences, but the school have no laboratory, no experiments are carried out and even there are no enough textbooks in the library, but all what is demanded from you is quality results, what can one do as a teacher? It is very impractical for sure. The only option is to resign or change the profession altogether.” (Interview Conducted on 24th September, 2017)

The sentiments by the Chemistry teacher was in consistent with most of the other teachers had to explain. This was because as indicated from the demographic data of teachers who had left, most of them taught Mathematics and science related subjects. The implication is that inadequate physical facilities for technical and vocational education and training as well as mechanisms will also affect the achievement 2030 agenda on industrialization. The study findings are in agreement with the study findings by Stewart (2012) that one of the most frequently cited sources of dissatisfaction in teachers is lack of enough learning and teaching resources in public schools in developing countries and in fact, many strongly resist posting to a rural school, resulting in losses of newly qualified teachers.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

The study did find out that working conditions in schools did influence teacher attrition in public secondary schools in Uasin Gishu County. specifically, unfriendly working conditions, students’ behaviour and discipline, school leadership and administration, heavy workload, ethnicity, lack of professional respect and teachers not involved in decisions making environmental situation fuelled high teacher attrition rate in schools. The study also found that some factors were related to teachers’ behaviours such as cases of amorous teachers, constant absenteeism (with no reason), conflicts with other teachers and school administration. School environment particularly schools located in remote areas with poor infrastructure and communication contributed to high incidents of attrition compared to those in urban areas. The study revealed that some principals’ leadership style was a factor that contributed to attrition while the negative perception of the profession by society, lack of adequate instructional and infrastructural materials for learning and teaching and incidences of the local community resistance of teachers and principals posted to schools. In conclusion, to this objective, it was clear that personal characteristics alternative employment (pull factors) and push factors (dissatisfaction with teaching) influenced majority of teachers to leave the profession in Uasin Gishu County. In recommendations, the Ministry of Education and the Teachers’ Service Commission should review the policy on the election of school prefects and hire professional counsellors for public secondary schools to deal with discipline related issues. The school management, especially the BOM need to consider teacher input during planning and decision-making.

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